

of items or entities must be used for the betterment of the economy and society as a whole (Einav and Levin, 2014). There has been a shift in consciousness about the value of statistics in reducing poverty. The topic of data governance, which has generated much discussion in developed economies, is also gaining traction in developing countries (Ladley, 2019). Despite this, there are still many difficult policy questions that have not been answered. Therefore, the World Bank Group (WBG) has undertaken surveys during the hard time of COVID-19 pandemic to evaluate the landscape of global data infrastructure and proposes high-level recommendations to establish an environment that is rich in data. On the other hand, the World Bank Group has released a complete report titled World Development Report 2021: Data for Better Lives (WDR 2021) on March 24, 2021 (World Bank, 2021). This report is licenced under the Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 IGO licence (CC BY 3.0 IGO). In addition to this, they have established a data website (<https://wdr2021.worldbank.org/data-and-research/>) with the purpose of archiving and disseminating all of the background data, events, data stories, and publications associated with this report in an open access environment in order to promote FAIR practise in a world that is constantly changing.

The WDR 2021 is a comprehensive and illuminating review of the potential of data to encourage long-term prosperity in order to accomplish the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and to monitor progress in fulfilling them. The report is divided into three sections and organized into nine chapters for logically exploring every aspect of the production, collection, management, benefits, sharing, use, reuse, misuse, barriers, ethics, infrastructures, systems and policies of public data. The first part of the report (advancing development objectives through data) contains first four chapters, the second part (aligning data governance with the social contract) holds the next five chapters, and the third part (moving toward an integrated national data system) carries the 9th chapter.

Chapter 1 (Harnessing the value of data for the poor) briefly describes the meaning, context, and value of data and explains how data could improve the lives of people in different ways. It discusses the process of transformation raw data into information, and then turning that information into insights that can be used to assist those who are less fortunate. However, this chapter also discusses the challenges involved in establishing a trusted environment that prevents the potentially harmful exploitation of data as it is transferred between parties and allows the creation of data that can be reused and utilized in other contexts. In order to make sure that the maximum potential value of data is utilized and shared in a manner that is both safe and equitable, it is necessary to have a robust data governance framework.

This framework should be composed of relevant policies, laws, regulations, and institutions.

Chapter 2 (Data as a force for public good) explains the transformative power of public intent data for government. It draws attention to the widespread disparities in the accessibility, accuracy, compatibility, and usefulness of these data, especially in low-income nations, which are those that stand to gain the most from better public intent data. Moreover, the creation of useful data for public policy is hampered by a lack of resources, data literacy, technical capability, and data governance. However, these issues can be overcome by giving data a high priority at a greater extent, along with funding over a long period of time, investments in human resources, and legislation supportive of the secure generation, collection, sharing, and use of data.

Chapter 3 (Data as a resource for the private sector) focuses on the data as a valuable asset for businesses. The open data provided by the government about the economic activities of businesses can be utilized as an input in data-driven decision-making, which can minimize compliance costs, thereby enhancing productivity, export competitiveness, and economic development. However, it also notes that the use of data by businesses can increase domestic inequalities in nations where fundamental skills, infrastructure, and funding are not commonly accessible. In addition to this, it may also make the playing field less favorable for less developed nations, the local businesses of which may have difficulty competing with huge international companies because to the economies of scale and scope that result from data. It also warns that policymakers should be cognizant of the risks that data use by enterprises poses for the concentration of economic power, structures of disparity, and safeguarding individual rights, despite the many potentials it brings for addressing development concerns.

Chapter 4 (Creative reuse of data for greater value) discusses the potential advantages of utilizing data, both public and private, for the purposes of growth. Repurposing data and integrating public and private data can lead to new breakthroughs and advancements in the delivery of services and in the formulation of public policy, respectively. On the other hand, there are possible dangers involved, such as the continuation of prejudice and worries about the safety of the data. According to the findings of the report, there is a need for government regulation and consumer protection measures, as well as expenditures in education, data partnerships, and research, in order to make efficient use of data obtained from private intent. In addition to this, it emphasizes the significance of taking into account and addressing any populations that may be overlooked, as well as determining the most effective procedures and making recommendations.

Chapter 5 (Data infrastructure policy: Ensuring equitable access for poor people and poor countries) discusses the policies surrounding data infrastructure to guarantee fair access for underprivileged individuals and underdeveloped nations. It is important for policymakers to facilitate the establishment of a local data infrastructure that facilitates the local data storage, processing, and share of data so that it is not necessary for the data to travel through distant overseas facilities. This would ensure equitable access to high-speed data at an affordable cost to the marginalized individuals of the poor nations.

Chapter 6 (Data policies, laws and regulations: Creating a trust environment) emphasises the significance of having a robust legal and regulatory framework in order to keep people's trust in the transactions using their data. This architecture ought to consist of not only enablers to allow access and reuse, but also protections to prevent the inappropriate use of data. Safeguards need to make a distinction between personal and non-personal data, and enablers for data sharing are better established for data collected with the intention of serving the public than for data collected privately. The establishment of a trustworthy environment is an on-going process that can take on a variety of forms and is subject to the regulatory system of each country. It also highlights the fact that there is no framework that is universally applicable and that safeguards and enablers may need to be tailored to local goals and capacities in countries with poor regulatory environments.

Chapter 7 (Creating value in the data economy: The role of competition, trade, and tax policy) warns that poor and middle-income countries face concerns due to the increased use of data in platform business models, which in turn affects competition, trade, and taxation in the real economy. Sharing data between market players can encourage competition, and how well data is protected will affect how data-enabled services are traded across borders. This means that how governments protect and use data will have an effect on the real economy. One of the greatest obstacles to raising more money through taxes is the nebulous character of digital value chains. Poor and middle-income nations typically aren't equipped to deal with these kinds of economic policy issues. The chapter contends that these problems require swift competition measures and cutting-edge trade and tax management. It also notes that enforcement of antitrust laws, regulation of technology providers, data standards, trade agreements, and taxation policies all have an effect on one another and that international coordination on these issues is necessary to ensure efficient and equitable data economy policies that meet the needs and interests of countries.

Chapter 8 (Institution for data governance: Building trust through collective action) describes the many roles necessary for efficient data governance. Strategic planning, drafting norms and standards, enforcing them, and producing the learning and

evidence required to gain insights and handle emerging difficulties all fall under this category. Furthermore, it emphasises the significance of non-governmental institutions and procedures, such as data intermediaries, in facilitating the secure sharing and use of data by governments and other actors in order to maximise value capture and ensure universal access. In order to effectively carry out their missions, public institutions need access to adequate funding, autonomy, and technological capacity (including data literacy), among other things, as discussed in this chapter. It also emphasises the need for influential politicians to support data management policies that foster a culture of openness and transparency, and encourage widespread data use and sharing. Institutions can increase their legitimacy, transparency, and accountability by adopting a multi-stakeholder, purpose-driven approach to data governance and management.

Chapter 9 (Creating an integrated national data system) explains how to develop a comprehensive, integrated and trustworthy national data system (the creation, flow, and use of data) in order to fully utilise the potential of data for economic growth, social progress, and overall development. The processes necessary to build such a system differ from country to country based on their data maturity, and once it is in place, it must be continuously upgraded using professional human resources from different stakeholders. It also discusses the steps of integrating civil society, government, academia, and the corporate sector into the national data system and integrating international and regional organizations for cross-border collaborations.

Spotlights are included at the end of each chapter throughout the report. These spotlights investigate a variety of policy issues in greater detail and highlight pertinent cases from low- and middle-income nations and around the globe. Nonetheless, the report's first section evaluates how data use and reuse can improve the development of public policies, programmes, and service delivery, market efficiency and private sector growth and job creation. In this section, a conceptual framework is presented, and it is accompanied by illustrations and instances drawn from recent experience in low- and middle-income nations. Data's potential benefits are explored, along with ways to protect against its potential harms, in the report's second section, which focuses on issues of governance, law, and policy. The purpose of this section is to demonstrate how data can be used to improve the lives of the poor by examining these problems. The final section of the report presents the report's vision for a unified national data system by bringing together its earlier sections.

REVIEW

The WDR21 explores the panorama of global data ecosystem to enhance the lives of marginalised people and establish a standard framework for data stewardship, citizen engagement, economic

development, and good governance. It highlights the major issues related to public data infrastructure, interoperability, accessibility, data privacy, and fear of misuse. Moreover, the report presents a data governance model aimed at maximizing the benefits of data while minimizing the risks of misuse. The authors argue that this model can help improve people's lives by utilizing data in a responsible and ethical way. The report also emphasised the significant value of data and called for the creation of a new social contract that would permit the use and redistribution of data for the purpose of generating economic and social value, guarantee everyone's fair and equal access to that value, promote trust, and encourages confidence that data would not be used in ways that would be harmful.

This report provides a critical perspective on the use of data in the pursuit of development goals by addressing two fundamental questions. First, how can data be used effectively to advance development agendas? Second, what type of data governance is required to ensure safe, ethical, and secure use of data while also ensuring equitable distribution of value? The report emphasises that the collection of additional data is not the solution and instead focuses on the efficient use of data that is already available to enhance the outcomes of development, particularly for people living in poverty in nations that are also poor. In addition to this, the research highlights the existing data deficits in impoverished nations, which is an issue that must be addressed in order to ensure that wealth is distributed fairly. The report examines

the new environment in response and offers decision-makers a framework for contemplating the challenges, possibilities, and drawbacks involved. It is evident that voices from countries with lower incomes need to be heard in these international discussions immediately.

The report is well-researched, well-written, and easy to understand, making it accessible to a wide audience. From this report government, policymakers, administrators, economists, data scientists, researchers, gender equality advocates, development professionals, civil society representatives, and funding bodies can predict their possible areas of investment. Universities and other academic institutions could invest in this area for research and development. However, the report suggests more international cooperation to establish a data vibrant ecosystem that will achieve the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in a better way. To sum up, the report is a must-read for everyone with an interest in learning how data may aid in fostering sustainable development.

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